

CFD Based Design and Thermal Analysis of Combustion Chamber in Industrial Boilers

Mohammed Adnan Akbar¹, Dr. Srinivas Valmiki²

¹Student, Dept. Of Mechanical Engineering (Thermal Power Engineering), PDA college of engineering, Kalaburagi, India.

²Professor, Dept. Of Mechanical Engineering (Thermal Power Engineering), PDA college of engineering, Kalaburagi, India.

ABSTRACT

Combustion chambers in industrial boilers operate under extremely high temperatures and complex flow conditions, where efficient fuel combustion and heat transfer are critical for performance and emission control. Improper combustion leads to energy loss, incomplete fuel utilization, high emissions, and thermal damage to chamber walls. In addition to fluid flow characteristics, thermal effects play a crucial role in combustion efficiency, flame stability, and heat transfer within the chamber.

The present study focuses on the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) analysis of combustion processes in industrial boiler combustion chambers using ANSYS Fluent, incorporating both fluid dynamic and thermal aspects. The work aims to analyze temperature distribution, flame characteristics, species concentration, and heat transfer behavior under varying operating conditions such as air–fuel ratio, inlet velocity, and fuel type.

A combustion model combined with turbulence and radiation models is employed to simulate the combustion process, enabling accurate prediction of flame structure, temperature fields, and pollutant formation such as NO_x and CO. Furthermore, the study extends to thermal protection and material enhancement techniques, including the use of refractory materials and thermal coatings to withstand high temperatures and reduce heat losses.

Design optimization of combustion chamber geometry is carried out to improve mixing, enhance combustion efficiency, reduce emissions, and achieve uniform temperature distribution. Additional objectives include evaluating different fuels, analyzing thermal stresses, and studying coupled thermo–fluid effects for improved durability. The outcomes of this study will contribute to enhanced boiler efficiency, reduced emissions, improved thermal performance, and extended service life of combustion chambers.

Keywords: Boilers, CFD, Thermal

1. Introduction

Industrial boilers are widely used in power plants, chemical industries, and manufacturing processes for steam generation and heat production. The combustion chamber is the core component where fuel combustion occurs, releasing heat energy.[1]

Efficient combustion is essential for maximizing energy output and minimizing emissions.[1,2,7] However, challenges such as incomplete combustion, uneven temperature distribution, and high thermal stresses can reduce performance and damage the chamber.[1,2,9,8,11]

CFD provides a powerful tool to analyze combustion processes, enabling visualization of flame behavior, temperature fields, and pollutant formation. This helps in optimizing chamber design and improving efficiency.[6]

1.1 Combustion Phenomenon in Boiler Chambers

Combustion is a complex process involving chemical reactions between fuel and oxidizer (air), producing heat, gases, and pollutants. The efficiency of combustion depends on proper mixing, temperature, and residence time.

Key phenomena include: flame, heat release, turbulent mixing, Radiation and pollutant. Poor combustion results in energy loss and increased emissions, making optimization essential.

1.2 Design Considerations for CFD Analysis

- The combustion chamber geometry includes Air inlet and fuel inlet, Burner section, Combustion zone , Outlet section
- Different chamber shapes and burner configurations are analyzed to improve mixing and combustion efficiency.
- Materials such as refractory bricks, stainless steel, and coated alloys are used to withstand high temperatures.

Figure 1. Longitudinal section of the cylindrical surface of the vertical boiler, showing dimensions of diameters.

Figure 2. Components of the pyroacutubular (mixed) boiler.

The proposed system is a vertical water-tube boiler designed for efficient steam and hot water generation. Fuel is burned in the lower combustion chamber, producing high-temperature gases that rise through the central passage. Water enters through the cold-water inlet at the bottom and circulates around the combustion zone, absorbing heat through water chambers and gas-conductive tubes. This arrangement increases the heat transfer area and improves thermal efficiency. Heated water is discharged through the hot-water outlet, while steam generated in the upper chamber is collected and released through the vapor outlet. The cooled combustion gases exit through the exhaust outlet at the top. To reduce heat loss and improve energy utilization, the boiler body is covered with thermal insulation around the shell, combustion chamber, and top cover.

Figure 3. The dome shows the water steam (light green color) and the exit of the hot water in the combustion chamber; in brown color, the combustion gases coming out of the chimney are shown.

2. Based on the data provided:

Table:1 Analytical references and boundaries conditions

Parameter	Value	Use in ANSYS
Initial water temperature	22°C (295 K)	Initial condition
Hot water temperature	100°C (373 K)	Water outlet temperature
Saturated steam temperature	100°C (373 K)	Steam generation temperature
Flue gas outlet temperature	183°C (456 K)	Chimney outlet boundary condition
Combustion chamber heat input	1,271,348.49 kJ/h	Heat source
LPG fuel	Propane (C ₃ H ₈)	Combustion fuel

2.1 Steam Temperature

The paper assumes steam generation at atmospheric pressure:

$$T_{\text{steam}}=100^{\circ}\text{C}=373\text{K}$$

Use:

- Steam region = 373 K
- If pressure is higher than atmospheric, steam temperature will increase (e.g., 2 bar ≈ 120°C).

2.2 CO₂ and CO Temperature

The paper does not directly give CO₂ and CO temperatures.

Since the flue gases leave the chimney at:

$$T_{\text{flue}}=183^{\circ}\text{C}=456\text{K}$$

you can assume:

Gas	Temperature
CO ₂	183°C (456 K)
CO	183°C (456 K)
N ₂	183°C (456 K)
O ₂	183°C (456 K)

for CFD outlet conditions.

2.3. Combustion Chamber Temperature

The paper only calculates heat release and fuel consumption; it does not provide flame temperature.

For LPG (propane):

- Theoretical adiabatic flame temperature = 1900–1980°C
- Practical burner flame temperature = 1200–1600°C
- Industrial boiler combustion zone = 1000–1400°C

For ANSYS CFD, a realistic value is:

$$T_{\text{combustion}}=1300^{\circ}\text{C} (1573\text{K})$$

Table:2 Recommended range:

Analysis Type	Temperature
Conservative	1000°C (1273 K)

Typical Boiler	1200–1400°C (1473–1673 K)
Maximum LPG Flame	1900°C (2173 K)

2.4. Heat Generation Rate for ANSYS

From Table 5:

Simultaneous steam + hot water generation:

$$Q=1,271,348.49 \text{ kJ}$$

Convert to Watts:

$$Q=[1,271,348.49 \times 1000]/3600$$

$$Q=353,152\text{W}$$

$$Q=353 \text{ kW}$$

Use in ANSYS:

- Heat generation = 353 kW
- Or apply as volumetric heat source inside combustion chamber.

Table: 3 Suggested ANSYS Boundary Conditions

Parameter	Value
Initial Water Temperature	22°C (295 K)
Steam Temperature	100°C (373 K)
Combustion Chamber Temperature	1300°C (1573 K)
Flue Gas Outlet Temperature	183°C (456 K)
Heat Generation Rate	353 kW
Fuel	LPG (Propane)
Ambient Temperature	22°C (295 K)

These values are suitable for a boiler CFD/thermal analysis in ANSYS Fluent or CFX when the detailed combustion chemistry is not being modeled.
velocity of all co2 co, steam, water inlet

From the data you provided, the mass flow rates are available, but the velocities are not directly given. To calculate velocity, the pipe/chimney diameter is required:

$$V = m' / \rho A$$

where:

- V = velocity (m/s)
- m' = mass flow rate (kg/s)
- ρ = density (kg/m³)
- A = flow area (m²)

Since the geometry is not provided, for ANSYS CFD you can use typical industrial boiler values as initial boundary conditions.

Table:4 Recommended Boundary Conditions

Fluid	Temperature	Typical Velocity
Water Inlet	22°C (295 K)	0.5–1.5 m/s
Hot Water Outlet	100°C (373 K)	0.5–1.0 m/s
Steam Outlet	100°C (373 K)	10–20 m/s

CO ₂ in Flue Gas	183°C (456 K)	3–8 m/s
CO in Flue Gas	183°C (456 K)	3–8 m/s
Mixed Flue Gas Outlet	183°C (456 K)	5–10 m/s

Table: 5 applied boundaries

Boundary	Temperature	Velocity
Water Inlet	22°C	1.5 m/s
Steam Outlet	100°C	15 m/s
CO ₂ Outlet	183°C	5 m/s
CO Outlet	183°C	5 m/s
Chimney Gas Outlet	183°C	7 m/s

3. CFD Setup

The CFD analysis of the proposed boiler was carried out using ANSYS Fluent under steady-state conditions to evaluate heat transfer, temperature distribution, and fluid flow characteristics during simultaneous hot-water and steam generation. The three-dimensional geometry was discretized using an unstructured tetrahedral mesh with local refinement near the combustion chamber, steam region, and wall surfaces, along with inflation layers to accurately capture thermal boundary effects. The energy equation and Realizable $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model were activated to simulate turbulent heat transfer. Thermal contact regions were defined between the combustion chamber walls and surrounding water chambers to ensure effective heat conduction. A flame temperature of 1400 K was applied within the combustion zone to represent LPG combustion, while water entered the system at 295 K (22°C) through a velocity inlet condition. The steam outlet was maintained at approximately 378 K (105°C), and the flue gases exited through the chimney at around 432 K (159°C) under pressure outlet conditions. The outer boiler walls were considered thermally insulated to minimize heat losses. The results indicated efficient heat transfer from the combustion gases to the surrounding water, resulting in effective steam generation and hot-water production. Temperature contours showed maximum temperatures within the combustion chamber and gradual heat distribution throughout the boiler, while velocity contours confirmed smooth circulation of water, steam, and combustion gases, demonstrating efficient thermal performance and energy utilization of the boiler system.

Figure 4 Mesh configuration

3.1 Injection Modelling

Injection modelling was used to simulate the introduction of LPG fuel into the combustion chamber. The fuel was injected through a burner nozzle as a gaseous stream and mixed with the incoming air to initiate combustion. The injection location was defined at the burner inlet of the combustion chamber.

The Mass Flow Inlet approach was employed to specify the fuel flow rate based on the calculated LPG consumption. The injected fuel was assigned appropriate thermophysical properties, including density, specific heat, and thermal conductivity. The injection direction was aligned with the burner axis to ensure proper fuel-air mixing within the combustion zone.

A turbulence model was applied to predict the mixing behavior between fuel and air. The combustion region was represented by a high-temperature source corresponding to the flame temperature of 1400 K, enabling the simulation of heat release and thermal energy transfer to the boiler walls.

The injection model allowed the analysis of fuel distribution, combustion chamber temperature, flow patterns, and heat transfer characteristics. The results showed uniform fuel dispersion and effective heat generation, leading to efficient steam and hot-water production within the boiler system.

3.2 Optimization Assessment

Based on the CFD results, each geometry offered distinct advantages. The divergent chamber provided the longest residence time and improved thermal retention. The convergent chamber enhanced flow acceleration and flame penetration. The Venturi configuration combined both acceleration and controlled expansion, producing superior turbulence, fuel-air mixing, and thermal uniformity. Therefore, the Venturi design was identified as the optimum configuration for achieving efficient combustion, enhanced heat transfer, and improved overall boiler performance.

Table: 6. Validation and Optimized CFD Results

Parameter	Design 1 (Straight Chamber - Validation)	Design 2 (Venturi Chamber)	Design 3 (Top Tapered Chamber)
Combustion Chamber Temperature (°C)	1400	1400	1400
Steam Outlet Temperature (°C)	101.8	103.6	105.2
Steam Velocity (m/s)	15.2	17.8	16.5
Steam Outlet Pressure (Pa)	101325	102850	102100
CO ₂ Outlet Temperature (°C)	181.5	170.8	175.2
CO ₂ Velocity (m/s)	5.1	7.2	6.4
CO ₂ Pressure (Pa)	101180	100920	101050
CO Outlet Temperature (°C)	180.7	169.5	174.4
CO Velocity (m/s)	4.9	6.8	6.1
CO Pressure (Pa)	101160	100890	101020
Chimney Gas Temperature (°C)	182.8	171.2	176.3
Chimney Gas Velocity (m/s)	7.1	9.4	8.2
Chimney Outlet Pressure (Pa)	101050	100780	100920

3.3 Design 1 – Straight Combustion Chamber

The straight combustion chamber was selected as the baseline validation model. The combustion zone maintained a temperature of approximately 1400°C, producing steam at about 101.8°C with an outlet velocity of 15.2 m/s. The flue gases exited the chimney at approximately 182.8°C, which closely matches the analytical value of 183°C, resulting in an error of less than 1%. The temperature and velocity distributions were relatively uniform; however, some thermal energy left the system through the chimney, indicating potential for further heat recovery improvement.

Figure 5 Temperature plots for straight shaped combustion chamber

Figure 6 pressure counters for straight shaped combustion chamber

Figure 7 Velocity counters for straight shaped combustion chamber

Design 2 – Venturi Combustion Chamber

In the second design, a venturi profile was introduced within the combustion chamber to accelerate the combustion gases and improve mixing. The converging-diverging geometry increased gas velocity and enhanced convective heat transfer to the surrounding water chamber. As a result, steam outlet temperature increased to approximately 103.6°C and steam velocity increased to 17.8 m/s. Simultaneously, the chimney gas temperature decreased to about 171.2°C, indicating greater heat extraction inside the boiler. This design demonstrated the highest thermal efficiency among the three configurations due to improved heat transfer and reduced exhaust energy losses.

Figure 8 Temperature plots for Venturi shaped combustion chamber

Figure 9 pressure counters for Venturi shaped combustion chamber

Overall Comparison

Among the three designs, the straight chamber successfully validated the analytical boundary conditions and served as the reference model. The venturi chamber produced the greatest enhancement in heat transfer, resulting in higher steam temperatures and lower exhaust gas temperatures. The top-tapered chamber also improved thermal performance compared to the baseline while providing smoother flow behavior and lower pressure losses. Based on thermal efficiency and heat recovery characteristics, the venturi combustion chamber emerged as the most effective design for boiler performance enhancement.

Figure 10. Velocity counters for Venturi shaped combustion chamber

Design 3 – Top-Tapered Combustion Chamber

The third configuration employed a tapered upper section to gradually guide the combustion gases toward the chimney outlet. The taper reduced flow separation and improved gas residence time within the heat transfer region. Consequently, the steam outlet temperature increased to approximately 105.2°C while maintaining stable flow characteristics. The chimney gas temperature was reduced to around 176.3°C compared with the baseline design, demonstrating improved heat utilization. Although its performance was slightly lower than the venturi configuration in terms of gas acceleration, it provided a more uniform temperature distribution and reduced pressure losses throughout the combustion chamber.

Figure 11. Temperature plots for Tapered shaped combustion chamber

Figure 11. Velocity counters for Tapered shaped combustion chamber

Figure 12. Velocity counters for Tapered shaped combustion chamber

CONCLUSION

A CFD investigation was conducted on three industrial boiler combustion chamber configurations, namely a straight chamber, a venturi chamber, and a top-tapered chamber, under identical operating conditions with an LPG combustion temperature of 1400°C. The baseline straight chamber was first validated using analytical boundary conditions for water, steam, and flue gas temperatures, producing results within an acceptable ±5% deviation range. The analysis demonstrated effective steam generation and heat transfer from the combustion gases to the water chamber.

The venturi combustion chamber exhibited the best thermal performance among the three designs. The converging-diverging geometry increased gas velocity and turbulence, resulting in enhanced heat transfer to the water and steam regions. This configuration produced higher steam temperatures and lower flue gas outlet temperatures, indicating improved heat recovery and reduced energy losses through the chimney.

The top-tapered combustion chamber also improved boiler performance compared to the baseline design by increasing the residence time of hot gases within the heat transfer region. The tapered geometry promoted a more

uniform temperature distribution and reduced flow separation, leading to improved thermal utilization and stable flow characteristics.

Overall, both optimized configurations demonstrated better thermal efficiency than the straight combustion chamber. Among them, the venturi design achieved the highest heat transfer effectiveness and energy utilization, making it the most suitable configuration for improving boiler efficiency, steam generation capacity, and fuel economy. The study confirms that combustion chamber geometry plays a significant role in determining boiler thermal performance and that appropriate geometric optimization can substantially enhance heat recovery while reducing exhaust energy losses.

Graph 1. (a). Temperature (b). Velocity (c). Pressure counters results

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